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A Proactive Approach to the Recovery and Recycling of Photovoltaic Modules

Si purification via chemical methods

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Prepared By:	Jonas Låstad, Jafar Safarian
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Table of contents

1.	Executive summary	1
2.	Planned criteria	2
3.	Introduction	3
3.1	Recycling and Circular Economy	3
3.2	Silicon purification by acidic solutions.....	4
3.3	Glass separation.....	5
3.4	Vacuum refining consideration.....	6
4.	Material and methods	7
4.1	Leaching trials	7
4.2	Characterization of leachate.....	9
4.3	Characterization of Si samples.....	9
5.	Results and Discussion	10
5.1	Electron microscopy examination of received PV-Si samples	10
5.2	Chemical composition of received PV Si.....	12
5.3	Leaching results	13
5.3.1	Leaching trials series I.....	13
5.3.2	SEM-EDS analysis of Sample I	13
5.3.3	SEM-EDS analysis of Sample II	15
5.3.4	Leaching trials series II.....	18
6.	Conclusion	26
7.	References	27

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List of figures

Figure 3-1 Impurities in MG-Si and EoL -Si PV, M is the combined impurity concentration in the EoL-Si PV. ...	4
Figure 3-2 Simple schematic overview of the leaching of MG-Si	4
Figure 4-1 PV scrap analysed in this paper: left PV1, right PV2	7
Figure 4-2 Leaching setup for second experimental series.....	9
Figure 5-1 BSE images of PV1.....	10
Figure 5-2 EDS map of PV1 sample.	10
Figure 5-3 BSE image of one PV2 fragment	11
Figure 5-4 EDS map of PV2 sample	11
Figure 5-5 Sample overview PV1 on the left and PV2 on the right.....	13
Figure 5-6 THE SURFACE FEATURES OF SOME PARTICLES FROM PV-Si I SAMPLE.....	14
Figure 5-7 The EDS point analysis of selected cross sectioned particles from PV-Si I sample.....	14
Figure 5-8 A SEM image of macro-particles in PV-Si sample II, and their EDS analysis spectra.....	15
Figure 5-9 The surface features of some particles from PV-Si II sample.	16
Figure 5-10 The surface features of some particles from PV-Si II sample.	17
Figure 5-11 BSE images of sample 4R PV treated with 0,01M NaOH at 60C.	18
Figure 5-12 EDS mapping of sample 4R treated with 0,01M NaOH at 60C.	18
Figure 5-13 BSE IMAGES OF PV LEACH RESIDUE FROM LEACHING TRIAL NR. 5.....	19
Figure 5-14 EDS MAPPING OF SAMPLE 5R TREATED WITH 0,01M NaOH AT 60C.	19
Figure 5-15 BSE IMAGES OF PV LEACH RESIDUE FROM LEACHING TRIAL NR. 6.....	20
Figure 5-16 EDS MAPPING OF SAMPLE 6R TREATED WITH 1M NaOH AT 25C.	20
Figure 5-17 BSE IMAGES OF PV LEACH RESIDUE FROM LEACHING TRIAL NR. 7.....	21
Figure 5-18 EDS MAPPING OF SAMPLE 7R TREATED WITH 0,01M NaOH AT 25C.	21
Figure 5-19 BSE IMAGES OF PV LEACH RESIDUE FROM LEACHING TRIAL NR. 8.....	22
Figure 5-20 EDS MAPPING OF SAMPLE 8R TREATED WITH 0,1M NAOH AT 35C.	22
Figure 5-21 GDMS analysis of NaOH leached PV1 samples.	23
Figure 5-22 GDMS analysis of Aqua Regia leached PV1 samples.....	24
Figure 5-23 Yield for leachate solution calculated from ICP-MS results compared to PV1-3.....	25
Figure 5-24 Powder residue from sample 13R leached with 1M NaOH for 6 hours.....	25

List of tables

Table 4-1 Experimental procedure for leaching trials performed in first trial series.....	7
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Table 4-2 Experimental procedure for leaching trials performed in second trial series.....	8
Table 5-1 Chemical analysis of starting material.	12

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

PV	Photovoltaic
EoL	End of life
SoG	Solar grade
MG	Metallurgical grade
C-Si	Crystalline silicone
PV	Photovoltaic
SEM	Scanning electron microscope
BSE	Backscattered electron (detector)
EDS	Energy dispersive spectroscopy
XRD	X-ray diffraction / diffractometry
ICP-MS	Inductively coupled plasma – mass spectroscopy
GDMS	Glow discharge mass spectroscopy

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1. Executive summary

The research plan for Task 4.1.1 is that the incoming recovered Si from WP2 CSP is checked for contamination (organics, glass, metals) at NTNU lab and, if required, a feedback loop will be established to achieve the required quality. In addition, as risk mitigation, if the received silicon contains organics, a combustion/gasification process at lab or pilot scale is employed to further refine the recovered Si. The plan is tried evaluating several leaching agents to remove impurities such as P, Al, Ag, Sn, etc as well as the heavy-doped layer on the surface of recovered wafer. Lab scale leaching reactors at NTNU have been used, to do the experimental work and optimize the process, simulations in HSC chemistry (software) will be run. The effects of different parameters will be studied experimentally, and the process optimized for upscaling (to obtain a recipe for WP5). Before the chemical purification, advanced material characterization has been carried out to define the microstructures of the above different layers.

2. Planned criteria

The research in this subtask 4.1.1 has been done by NTNU. This part of the research is focusing on extra chemical process application prior high temperature melting and refining of received Si particles from WP2. A primary objective is to characterize the received recovered Si particles in WP2 by different characterization techniques. This will provide information about the morphology, microstructure and particulate contaminations in the received materials. Obviously, this outlines the strategy for further processing of the received Silicon material. In this regard, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Inductively-coupled Plasma-Mass Spectroscopy (ICP-MS) and Glow Discharge Mass Spectroscopy (GDMS) techniques are used at NTNU lab. In addition, the materials are characterised at SINTEF lab, and Fraunhofer CSP and all the obtained data are shared and evaluated with the partners. The secondary objective is to investigate various chemical agents to remove the existing impurities in the received silicon samples. In this case, both acidic and basic solutions are tried and evaluated. A key criterion is to upgrade the purity of the received silicon as much as possible to minimize the costs related to the later high temperature vacuum and gas refining techniques. Obtaining a silicon with a purity over 99.999%Si with P and B concentrations below 2ppmw will be suitable for this part of the research.

3. Introduction

3.1 Recycling and Circular Economy

Despite this, the recycling of PV modules is not a well-established process, and the present technology is optimized for recovery of high value and not bulk materials. It is difficult to create a standardized method, as the PV modules are complex. Additionally, the low weight percentage of the valuable metals from EoL-silicon solar cells has been a deterrent to proactive recycling efforts. Consequently, the cost of recycling often is outweighed by the less expensive and accessible disposal and landfilling^[14]. By recovering valuable materials from EoL-PV modules, the total energy required to extract, transport, and refine raw materials for new production will be reduced. Beyond the environmental benefits, recycling reinforces the supply chain stability and the development of new market opportunities both domestically and internationally. Studies indicate that the recycling of PV modules could turn profitable at 19,000 tonnes/year, meaning that the current smaller-scale operations are not yet economically viable¹. Reports suggest that recycling a PV module in the U.S. can cost between \$15 to \$45, while disposal fees at non-hazardous landfills may be under \$1 per module, and under \$5 per module at hazardous waste landfills². The need for photovoltaics (PV) recycling is becoming increasingly urgent due to its widespread use, and short lifespan. IRENA estimates that the cumulative global PV waste will approach 80 million tons by 2050. There are varying PV technologies of which Si based PVs represents 92% of the market and are of main interest. Other technologies such as two thin film PV panels or more novel ones represents the remaining market and should not be recycled in the same process. Due to this smaller demand and different chemistry, they will not be considered for this paper.

Separation methods exist for achieving high recovery of the various components of the panels, however the recycling of silicon which represents only about 3 wt% and less of the value of the PV module has been of lower priority for recovery. The challenge in achieving complete recycling of C-Si PVs is the required purity of the Si. End of life silicon from PVs fall in between the purity of high-quality metallurgical grade silicon (MG-Si) at 98 wt%- and Solar grade silicon (SoG-Si) at 99.99wt%. This causes a disparity between the value of the Si and its potential value. While the high purity makes it more than the required purity for metallurgical grade silicon, thereby being lost value. With the impurities largely being isolated outside of the bulk Si, methods such as chemical and mechanical separation offers the feasibility of purifying the recovered Si. Methods such as etching exist for removal of surface contamination from the Si, however some elements are resistant to etching and remain. Original impurities and dopants as well as minor elements which as entered the Si through diffusion will remain in the silicon. This is presented in Figure 3-1.

¹ Choi and Fthenakis, "Crystalline Silicon Photovoltaic Recycling Planning."

² Lunardi et al., "Comparative Life Cycle Assessment of End-of-Life Silicon Solar Photovoltaic Modules."

FIGURE 3-1 IMPURITIES IN MG-Si AND EoL -Si PV, M IS THE COMBINED IMPURITY CONCENTRATION IN THE EoL-Si PV. ³

3.2 Silicon purification by acidic solutions

Leaching is a hydrometallurgical process that involves dissolving a soluble component from a solid into a liquid through a reaction at the solid-liquid interface. This method can be effective on silicon refining due to its high chemical resistance, which allows the impurities on its surface to be selectively removed. Leaching is used as a method to purify MG-Si, as illustrated in Figure 3-2. During solidification of MG-Si, impurities precipitate at the grain boundaries. Consequently, when MG-Si is ground into smaller particles, breaking along these boundaries, exposing the impurities to the surface ready to react to leaching agents⁴. The leaching process aims to maximize the removal of impurities while minimizing the loss of silicon. Achieving high purity is crucial for the semiconductor and solar industries, as even trace amounts of certain impurities can significantly impact the electrical properties of silicon.

FIGURE 3-2 SIMPLE SCHEMATIC OVERVIEW OF THE LEACHING OF MG-Si⁵.

³ Lu et al., “Thermodynamic Criteria of the End-of-Life Silicon Wafers Refining for Closing the Recycling Loop of Photovoltaic Panels.”

⁴ Safarian, Tranell, and Tangstad, “Processes for Upgrading Metallurgical Grade Silicon to Solar Grade Silicon.”

⁵ Xi et al., “Removal of Impurities from Metallurgical Grade Silicon with Metal Assisted Chemical Leaching.”

A range of leaching agents, such as acids, bases, and complex agents are typically used, depending on the impurities present with the silicon. For removing metallic elements, acidic solutions like HCl or HNO_3 are used. Acids like hydrofluoric acid HF can dissolve silicon directly and are used to remove metal impurities through the formation of complexes. Impurities in the form of silicon oxides can be digested acids such as H_3PO_4 as well as some of the metallic impurities, however this process is enhanced using HNO_3 and HF .⁶ Alkaline solutions such as $NaOH$ will digest some metallic impurities and will digest both glass and silicon, and has been used in achieving a silicone with a purity approaching 4N.⁷

Several other parameters influence the efficiency of the leaching processes, including temperature, leaching agent concentration, duration, flow conditions, and particle size. The concentration of the leaching agent is particularly critical, as excessive concentrations can lead to significant silicon loss. Higher temperatures enhance the leaching rate, providing the energy to chemical bonds. F. Ebrahimfar and M. Ahmadian⁸ studied the purification of MG-Si through acid leaching, analyzing the different parameters with acidic leaching agents HNO_3 , H_2SO_4 , HCl , and HF influence the process. They found that impurity removal from MG-Si is more effective with smaller particles and higher temperatures.

3.3 Glass separation

There is a range glasses with varying composition used in PVs, soda-Lime glass, borosilicate glass, lead crystal glass, containing elevated concentrations of Al , B , Ca , K , and Pb .⁹ Common impurities such as S , F , Fe , Mn , As , Sb , Cd , Sn , Se in glass might also pose a challenge although, the glass used is often low iron glass, however some may remain. Anti-reflective coating usually composed of MgF , SiN , SiO , TiO and AlO is also often used which also can contaminate the Si .¹⁰ Recycling can induce small glass particles in the recovered silicon. Glass can also enter the waste stream in the if the panel has been damaged during use, in which case the separation of the glass becomes difficult. These glass shards contain metallic impurities which will enter the silicon when molten down for recasting or further treatment. The removal of these glass particles should improve the purity of the recirculated Silicon.

⁶ Park and Park, "Wet Etching Processes for Recycling Crystalline Silicon Solar Cells from End-of-Life Photovoltaic Modules."

⁷ Yi et al., "Recovering Valuable Metals from Recycled Photovoltaic Modules."

⁸ Ebrahimfar and Ahmadian, "Purification of Metallurgical-Grade Silicon by Acid Leaching."

⁹ Phoebe, *The Encyclopedia of Glass*.

¹⁰ Sharma, "Effect of Obliquity of Incident Light on the Performance of Silicon Solar Cells."

3.4 Vacuum refining consideration

The method of vacuum refining utilizes the difference in vapor pressure between the contaminants in the silicon and the silicon bulk. Vacuum refining is performed at high temperatures, but does not require the melting of the silicon, however this will access bulk impurities such as dopants. This method has been investigated by Safarian and Tangstad¹¹ showing the relation between temperature, pressure, and volatility. Their paper found that elements such as Pb, Bi highly susceptible to vacuum refining, P, Zn, Na, Mg, Sb, In, Ca, Ag, Sn and Ga are also removable by this treatment. While elements such as Mn, Al Cu and Fe will see a slight purifying effect.

With a combined process of hydro- and vacuum metallurgy, the range of impurities can be covered. However achieving purification of boron, it theorized to require grain refining such as with high purity Pb or Zn.¹² The ability to extract these elements by combined process of chemical and vacuum metallurgy lowers their priority in chemical refinement. However, it would be best to remove the elements with low volatility in the vacuum refining with the chemical methods. This may be beneficial for both later processes of vacuum refining and directional solidification. The method of vacuum refining utilizes the difference in vapor pressure between the contaminants in the silicon and the silicon bulk. Vacuum refining is performed at high temperatures, but does not require the melting of the silicon, however this will access bulk impurities such as dopants. This method has been investigated by Tangstad and Safarian¹³ showing the relation between temperature, pressure, and volatility. Their paper found that elements such as Pb, Bi highly susceptible to vacuum refining, P, Zn, Na, Mg, Sb, In, Ca, Ag, Sn and Ga are also removable by this treatment. While elements such as Mn, Al Cu and Fe will see a slight purifying effect however not sufficient for effective removal. With a combined process of hydro- and vacuum metallurgy, the range of impurities can be covered. However achieving purification of boron, it theorized to require grain refining such as with high purity Pb or Zn. Beyond boron, the main impurities commonly found in recycled solar panel chips which have low removability in the vacuum step and therefore of high importance for removal in the chemical step is Fe, Cu, Mn, Co, Ni, Sn, Ga, and Ge.¹⁴

¹¹ Safarian and Tangstad, Merete, "Compendium: New Solar Grade Silicon Production Processes."

¹² Lu et al., "Thermodynamic Criteria of the End-of-Life Silicon Wafers Refining for Closing the Recycling Loop of Photovoltaic Panels."

¹³ Safarian and Tangstad, Merete, "Compendium: New Solar Grade Silicon Production Processes."

¹⁴ Lu et al., "Thermodynamic Criteria of the End-of-Life Silicon Wafers Refining for Closing the Recycling Loop of Photovoltaic Panels."

4. Material and methods

As the PVs are recycled the modules are deconstructed and the EVA is removed using pyrolysis, leaving behind the silicon wafer, tabbing and coating attached. This process also leaves behind microscopic particles of glass from the protective layer of tempered glass. This material has is what is studied in this paper. As presented in Figure 4-1 PV1 as shown on the left is visually homogeneous with silvery silicon metal in uniform granulates, while PV2 as shown on the right has the blue tint of silicon nitride, as well as including foreign fragments. The experiments were performed in two series the first as a part of a master thesis and the second as the initial results of a PhD.

FIGURE 4-1 PV SCRAP ANALYSED IN THIS PAPER: LEFT PV1, RIGHT PV2

4.1 Leaching trials

A range of reagents was studied for the removal of impurities from the PV chips. Previous work was performed analyzing the effects of the agents HCl , HNO_3 and the two following each other and are referenced as the trials A-E. The samples will hereby be referred to by their Trial Nr. ICP-MS samples will include the time of sampling in the sample id. The experimental condition for this series is presented in Table 4-1. Note that trial A and B consists of 3 separate batches of PV where the results were combined, and trial E consists of the same batch of PV being treated twice.

TABLE 4-1 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE FOR LEACHING TRIALS PERFORMED IN FIRST TRIAL SERIES.

Trial Nr.	Sample	Molarity [M]	Reagent	Time [min]	Temp [C°]	Volume [mL]	Sample mass [g]
A	PV1	1.58	HCl	120	60	1000*3	100*3
B	PV1	3.15	HCl	120	60		
C	PV1	4.73	HCl	120	60		
D	PV1	0.79	HNO ₃	120	60	1000*3	100*3
E	PV1	1.59	HNO ₃	120	60		
F	PV1	2,38	HNO ₃	120	60		

The leaching performed in the second leaching trial series is denoted as trial nr. 1-22. Trials Nr. 9 and 10 were blank trials used for reference. Trial no. 22 was performed without leaching agent, however, was a study of the effect of pure washing in water. All trials were performed at liquid to solid ratio of 10 and stir rate of 300 RPM for ease of comparison. The conditions used is presented in Table 4-2.

TABLE 4-2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE FOR LEACHING TRIALS PERFORMED IN SECOND TRIAL SERIES.

Trial Nr.	Sample	Molarity [M]	Reagent	Time [min]	Temp [C°]	Volume [mL]	Sample mass [g]
1	PV1	0.5	NaOH	30	60	1000	100
2	PV1	1	NaOH	30	60	1000	100
3	PV1	0.1	NaOH	120	60	500	50
4	PV1	0.01	NaOH	120	60	500	50
5	PV1	0.1	NaOH	120	25	500	50
6	PV1	1	NaOH	120	25	500	50
7	PV1	0.01	NaOH	120	25	500	50
8	PV1	0.1	NaOH	120	35	500	50
9	-	-	-		-	500	-
10	-	0.1	NaOH		-	500	-
11	PV1	0.1	NaOH	360	60	500	50
12	PV1	0.1	NaOH	360	25	500	50
13	PV1	1	NaOH	360	25	500	50
14	PV1	1 : 3	HNO ₃ : HCl	1200	60	500	50
15	PV1	1 : 3	HNO ₃ : HCl	1200	25	500	50
16	PV2	1 : 3	HNO ₃ : HCl	1200	60	500	50
17	PV1	2 : 6	HNO ₃ : HCl	1200	60	500	50
18	PV1	2 : 6	HNO ₃ : HCl	1200	25	500	50
19	PV2	2 : 6	HNO ₃ : HCl	1200	60	500	50
20	PV2	0.1	NaOH	120	60	500	50
21	PV2	1	NaOH	120	25	500	50
22	PV1	-	-	60	25	500	50
23	PV1	14.615	H ₃ PO ₄	360	60	500	50
24	PV1	1	H ₃ PO ₄	360	60	500	50

The second leaching trial series was performed parallelly in 3 PTFE beakers using a water bath to achieve uniform temperature as presented in Figure 4-2. Lids were placed on top to achieve a more uniform temperature. The ICP-MS samples were taken as a function of time providing some kinetic data. When finished the samples were filtered and washed by rinsing with distilled water. The analysis of trials 23 and 24 has not concluded as of publication of this paper.

FIGURE 4-2 LEACHING SETUP FOR SECOND EXPERIMENTAL SERIES

4.2 Characterization of leachate

The leachate was analysed using ICP-MS sampling the reaction at minutes 1, 30, 120. Some samples which ran for longer were sampled at the end of their reaction, 360 and 1200 minutes respectively. The ICP-MS were done in two series, one which was performed with the elements Ag, Al, Ca, Cu, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, P, Si, Sn, Ti, Zn, while later analysis added the elements B, Ni, and Pb. As the samples were too concentrated for ICP-MS analysis, the samples were diluted 50x by sampling 1 ml from the reactor to a small beaker then diluting 0,3 ml of that solution in a 15 mL sample vial using distilled water. The analysis was performed by the Department of Chemistry at NTNU using a NexION 5000 Multi-Quadrupole ICP-MS.

4.3 Characterization of Si samples.

The SEM used for this paper was a JEOL IT800 using a BSE detector, achieving elemental contrast, as well as EDS analysis including mapping. The samples were intentionally not casted in polymer and polished to preserve the surface structure of the samples. Instead, they were glued in using carbon glue and pushed to lay flat on the surface.

GDMS analyses were performed on PV1 and PV2 and all the solid samples from the second leaching trial series. The elements studied were B, Na, MG, Al, Si, P, Ca, Ti, Mn, Fe, Ni, Cu, Zn, and Ag for trials. The analysis was performed by the Department of Materials Science and Engineering at NTNU using a Nu Instruments – Astrum – GDMS. A few grains of the sample were attached in a plate of indium and placed in a partial vacuum covered by Argon gas.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Electron microscopy examination of received PV-Si samples

The received PV1 sample was visually homogeneous, however, BSE analysis in SEM indicates a large amount of metallic and nonmetallic impurities on the surface as seen in Figures 5-1 and 5-2. EDS analysis indicates these particles to be composed of mainly Ag, Zn, while some particles indicate Ti. There is little indication of oxides in the image. The elemental sensitivity is too low to yield accurate quantitative data for EDS analysis.

FIGURE 5-1 BSE IMAGES OF PV1

FIGURE 5-2 EDS MAP OF PV1 SAMPLE.

PV 2 which was untreated and was composed of multiple different grains, one such grain, is presented in Figure 5-3, where the surface structure does not indicate a highly inhomogeneous composition. However, observing the microchemical data, as presented in the EDS map in Figure 5-4 lines of Ag, can be seen. More notable is the distribution of the Si, which seems to be covered by a layer of In, providing a high yield on the side of the sample, rather than the main face. This could be the result of a dopant layer. The high boron content is only significant in the carbon glue.

FIGURE 5-3 BSE IMAGE OF ONE PV2 FRAGMENT

FIGURE 5-4 EDS MAP OF PV2 SAMPLE

5.2 Chemical composition of received PV Si

Composition of the received recovered wafers is presented in Table 5-1, and shows the levels of impurities in parts per billion. The impurities are summarized in the bottom of the table, however as the not all elements were analyzed for all the samples, this value might be misleading. PV0, and PV2-1 was analyzed in the first experimental series and PV3 was analyzed by Sintef. PV0 and PV1 both being treated using the same process by the same provider, was assumed to be similar. Some differences are observed, which would be expected as the GDMS analysis has issues with producing representative results. The ICP-MS data is however assumed to be more representative. The significant levels of Al, Mg, and Ca in the samples was what prompted the theory of glass particles. The untreated sample indicates a high level of Ca contamination, along with significant levels of Mg, Mn, and Ag as well as elevated levels of most other elements. Observing the analysis of the treated samples PV0 and PV1, most of the impurities has been removed, while the levels of Al, Ca, Mn, Ag and Sn remains high. Combining the levels of impurities using the values found using ICP-MS, we find that PV1 has a purity of 99.98%, or 3N, while PV2 has a purity of 99.61% or 2N. This is in line with expectations.

TABLE 5-1 CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF STARTING MATERIAL.

Element [ppb]	PV0 GDMS	PV1-1 GDMS	PV1-2 GDMS	PV1-3 ICP-MS	PV2-1 GDMS	PV2-2 ICP-MS
B	712	84	97	648	648	260
Na	-	513	63	-	-	-
Mg	127	77	77	6 546	7	144 000
Al	52 046	344	281	34 777	34 777	25 000
P	213	385	291	773	773	4 600
Ca	93 536	1 249	270	27 354	27 354	3 453 000
Ti	161	246	310	2 880	2 880	6 600
V	4	6	-	76	76	500
Cr	4 895	-	-	523	523	50
Mn	607	11	23	11 504	11 504	250
Fe	5 784	167	360	4 567	4 567	2 600
Ni	18 355	123	288	1 227	1 227	450
Cu	1 510	557	828	1 302	1 302	7 800
Zn	-	12 574	19 526	1 191	1 191	500
Ga	85	115	-	56	56	0
Ag	-	28 635	46 742	42 927	42 927	214 000
Sn	-	-	-	21 043	21 043	28 000
SUM	178 035	32 512	49 676	157 394	150 854	3887 610

5.3 Leaching results

5.3.1 Leaching trials series I

The prepared metallography samples from the two received silicon samples from Fraunhofer indicated that in the PV-Si I we had less impurities compared with the PV-Si II sample as illustrated Figure 5-5. Naked eye examination of PV-II sample indicated 11 macro particles with different colours and shapes as seen in the figure. In the following the results of electron microscopy study of the two samples are provided, for two types of samples; mounted in resin and morphologies of particulate samples.

FIGURE 5-5 SAMPLE OVERVIEW PV1 ON THE LEFT AND PV2 ON THE RIGHT.

5.3.2 SEM-EDS analysis of Sample I

The morphology study of PV-Si I indicated that the silicon particles have different surface features/texture as seen in Figure 5-6, and they do not show big impurity particles of metals, glass, etc.

FIGURE 5-6 THE SURFACE FEATURES OF SOME PARTICLES FROM PV-Si I SAMPLE.

The SEM analysis of PV-Si I sample mounted in resin indicated that when cross sections of the particles are prepared, they show the existence of different phases for some of the individual plate-like silicon particles as seen in Figure 5-7. As we see the main phase analysis by EDS reveals that it is pure silicon, however, the particle has metallic impurities on the surface and the metallic layers may contain Sn, Ag, Cu, Ca metals.

FIGURE 5-7 THE EDS POINT ANALYSIS OF SELECTED CROSS SECTIONED PARTICLES FROM PV-Si I SAMPLE.

5.3.3 SEM-EDS analysis of Sample II

From macroscopic examination by eye and binocular microscope several different particles regarding the shape and color were found as seen in Figure 5-8. The EDS analysis indicated that particle 1 is silicon particle, while particle 2 indicated Al and O as the main components. Wire-shape particle 3 was found to be mostly consisted of Cu and Sn metals. Particle 4 contains Si, Ca, Na and O and is most likely a glass particle.

FIGURE 5-8 A SEM IMAGE OF MACRO-PARTICLES IN PV-Si SAMPLE II, AND THEIR EDS ANALYSIS SPECTRA.

The morphology of PV-Si sample II in SEM indicated that the macro silicon particles are different compared to the PV-Si sample I mostly due to the presence of many small particles on the surface of Si plates as seen in Figure 5-9.

FIGURE 5-9 THE SURFACE FEATURES OF SOME PARTICLES FROM PV-Si II SAMPLE.

More particles in PV-Si II sample were characterized as illustrated in Figure 5-10. According to the EDS analysis, particles 6, 8 and 9 are silicon particles (as particle 1 in the above Figure 5-10). Particle 7 is consisted of mainly Al and O, and minor Si content, and it is more like particle 2 mentioned above. Particle 5 is a glass particle with the same elements as in particle 4 above and particle 6 was found to be Ag with some impurities of O, Pb, Si, Al, ect. Clearly PV2 has much more contamination from macroparticles, and more nanoparticles on the surface in comparison with PV-Si II sample.

FIGURE 5-10 THE SURFACE FEATURES OF SOME PARTICLES FROM PV-Si II SAMPLE.

5.3.4 Leaching trials series II

Sample 4R presented in Figure 5-11 and Figure 5-13 having the conditions of 0,01M NaOH at 60C indicating a reduction in surface contaminants, however some particles remain, particularly the spot of Ca in the EDS map, indicates that the glass particles were not removed effectively.

FIGURE 5-11 BSE IMAGES OF SAMPLE 4R PV TREATED WITH 0,01M NaOH AT 60C.

FIGURE 5-12 EDS MAPPING OF SAMPLE 4R TREATED WITH 0,01M NaOH AT 60C.

Figure 5-13 and Figure 5-14 presents sample 5R treated with 0,1 M NaOH at 25C shows a lot of surface features as well as a lot of heavy particulates. This sample also indicate remaining glass particulate, as seen by the oxygen and Calcium concentration in the EDS map.

FIGURE 5-13 BSE IMAGES OF PV LEACH RESIDUE FROM LEACHING TRIAL NR. 5

FIGURE 5-14 EDS MAPPING OF SAMPLE 5R TREATED WITH 0,01M NaOH AT 60C.

Figure 5-15 and Figure 5-17 shows the sample 6R which was leached at 1M NaOH and 25C. The BSE image indicates a high rate of Si digestion as the surface topology is distinctly different from that of PV1 with indication of pitting. The EDS map indicate a reduction in surface contamination, with some Ag particles.

FIGURE 5-15 BSE IMAGES OF PV LEACH RESIDUE FROM LEACHING TRIAL NR. 6

FIGURE 5-16 EDS MAPPING OF SAMPLE 6R TREATED WITH 1M NaOH AT 25C.

Figure 5-17 and Figure 5-18 presents the images of sample 7R with what looks to be high intergranular digestion. The EDS map indicate high metallic particles. The rough surface topology indicates could trap nanoparticles and therefore yield low purification. There is little indication for the presence of Glass contamination, however there is some points of increased oxygen concentration.

FIGURE 5-17 BSE IMAGES OF PV LEACH RESIDUE FROM LEACHING TRIAL NR. 7

FIGURE 5-18 EDS MAPPING OF SAMPLE 7R TREATED WITH 0,01M NaOH AT 25C.

Figure 5-19 and Figure 5-20 presents SEM images and EDS images these images present a high amount of both metallic and glass particles distributed on the rough surface.

FIGURE 5-19 BSE IMAGES OF PV LEACH RESIDUE FROM LEACHING TRIAL NR. 8

FIGURE 5-20 EDS MAPPING OF SAMPLE 8R TREATED WITH 0,1M NAOH AT 35C.

The physical separation trial conducted using a 100- μm mesh and rinsing water yielded abnormally high values for the impurities, above the level of the starting sample of PV1. It was therefore excluded from the graph. The etched granulates from the NaOH leaching trials is presented in Figure 5-21. The figure presents the elements which were analysed. Due to issues regarding the trial setup nr. 1 and 2 and were excluded. Further considering the heterogeneousness of the samples the GDMS results could be affected by the variation in local composition and therefore be non-representative. The fine residue separated during filtration as shown in Figure 5-24 could majorly affect the final purity if not properly separated. Variations in the known surface contamination should therefore be interpreted carefully and considered with respect to the ICP-MS data. Furthermore, the introduction contamination from the leaching solution is possible, the ICP-MS analysis of the blank NaOH solution indicates the presence of different alkaline elements as well as some copper and zinc. The ICP-MS analysis of the aqua regia trials indicated lower levels of contaminants, primarily Ca, K and Al. This could if not properly, rinsed contaminate the surface of the sample. The analysed residue from the NaOH leaching trials indicate that the leaching agent can be useful in reducing the concentration of impurities such as Mg, Al, P, Ca, Ti, as well as Ni, Cu, Zn, and Ag.

FIGURE 5-21 GDMS ANALYSIS OF NAOH LEACHED PV1 SAMPLES.

PV1 was also treated with aqua regia showing promising results with respect to the total levels of impurities, with most elements having reduced concentrations. Ag sees a large reduction. This data is presented in Figure 5-22.

FIGURE 5-22 GDMS ANALYSIS OF AQUA REGIA LEACHED PV1 SAMPLES.

Results of the chemical analysis of the chemically leached PV1 samples as presented in Figure 5-23 indicate that there is an issue with contamination from the leachate. It is assumed that impurities can be introduced via the NaOH or the surfaces of the containers used to prepare the samples. The leaching agents used for the aqua regia trials were of higher purity than the NaOH used. Future trials should make further effort to avoid this by rinsing more thoroughly also using higher purity water such as deionized water as well as handling more carefully. The samples leached for longer can be seen to yield higher purity, providing high aqueous recovery of Mg, P, and Ca. other elements such as Ni, Cu, Zn, Sn can also be seen enter the solution while also being correlated with the liberation and separation by filtration which does not present in the table. Phosphor removal is primarily correlated with the samples with higher silicon digestion which indicates that the surface dopant layer has been digested liberating the phosphor. The ICP-MS analysis indicates no digestion of boron which needs to be explained. Sample 6R also yielded higher purity. The assumption here is that the combined effect of higher temperature and concentration yielded higher digestion. ICP-MS data is required to analyze the selectivity of the leaching trials. The filtered only sample trial provided unexpected results with high recovery of P, K, Ca, Cu, Zn and Sn and Pb. This should indicate that these impurities are contained in free particles which could be physically separated, however P is known to be a dopant, unless a significant fraction of the P is contained in surface particulates. The physical separation method should be further investigated. Combined with the abnormally high values found by the GDMS analysis this indicates contamination.

Yield [ug/L]	Mg	Al	Si	P	K	Ca	Ti	Mn	Fe	Ni	Cu	Zn	Ag	Sn	Pb
0.5MNaOH 60C	4,0	40,9	1598392,0	72,3	2474,9	18,8	3,9	14,9	16,7	0,0	32,9	12,7	2,7	119,1	0,0
1 NaOH 60C	18,9	113,2	1581192,6	88,7	5355,2	246,8	5,8	52,0	51,3	0,0	115,2	43,6	5,0	181,0	0,0
0,1MNaOH 60C	0,0	15,9	4286365,8	117,2	72,7	0,0	7,0	0,5	1,3	0,0	2,2	3,6	82,7	545,8	0,0
0,01MNaOH 60C	0,0	11,9	549898,7	34,5	0,0	0,0	15,1	0,7	0,0	0,0	40,3	3,0	227,6	1471,2	0,0
0,1MNaOH 25C	0,2	23,6	21847,7	8,7	21,6	0,0	1,3	0,0	11,4	0,0	14,5	1,8	81,3	21,1	0,0
1MNaOH 25C	9,1	25,8	3089759,3	132,4	4091,9	159,9	6,5	8,7	19,6	0,0	74,1	35,4	14,8	113,1	0,0
0,01MNaOH 25C	0,0	3,0	9069,2	3,9	0,0	0,0	0,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	3,3	0,0	49,2	107,5	0,0
0,1MNaOH 35C	0,0	13,0	1397623,7	60,2	59,8	0,0	29,3	0,0	2,1	0,0	4,1	0,8	42,6	935,4	0,0
0,1MNaOH 60C 360min	546,0	0,0	6923933,5	305,5	530,0	7534,0	7,0	30,5	0,0	21,5	89,5	77,0	70,5	220,0	1,5
0,1MNaOH 25C 360min	536,0	0,0	474349,0	27,5	444,0	7289,0	0,0	1,5	0,0	32,5	123,5	95,0	260,0	530,0	3,5
1MNaOH 25C 360min	509,0	0,0	11111877,0	502,0	3472,5	4336,0	25,0	92,5	0,0	21,0	96,0	73,0	266,5	942,5	1,5
1:3M Aq. Regia 60C	35,0	0,0	4200,5	0,0	2,5	0,0	0,0	83,0	826,5	0,0	0,0	22,5	2392,5	130,5	14,5
1:3M Aq. Regia 25C	224,2	188847,4	25298,6	0,0	0,0	0,0	16,8	795,8	960,3	15,7	278,3	0,0	6242,8	831,5	0,0
2:6M Aq. Regia 60C	0,0	775,6	0,0	48,4	0,0	14,9	4,9	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	6666,1	788,2	0,0
2:6M Aq. Regia 25C	0,0	3451,7	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	5159,6	1198,1	0,0
Filter only	0,0	3540,8	36772,0	319,5	34816,3	6663,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	31,4	343,8	470,6	92,8	1920,6	26,2

FIGURE 5-23 YIELD FOR LEACHATE SOLUTION CALCULATED FROM ICP-MS RESULTS COMPARED TO PV1-3.

The ICP-MS analysis also indicated the presence of nanoparticles which is expected to largely be particles of silver and other indigestible metallic particles. The powder recovered from sample 13 which is presented in Figure 5-24. This powder was analyzed and found to contain primarily silver, zinc and sodium silicate.

FIGURE 5-24 POWDER RESIDUE FROM SAMPLE 13R LEACHED WITH 1M NaOH FOR 6 HOURS.

6. Conclusion

The received silicon batches from WP2 were experimentally characterised and further leached by several acidic and basic solutions to evaluate possibilities for further purification of silicon. The main obtained conclusions are summarised as follows.

- Received silicon particles have different levels of impurity, and the silicon particles show different surface morphologies and texture.
- The particulate impurities can be classified in micro and nano size, and in each group different chemical compositions were found.
- Contamination in the PV-SI is primarily Al, Ag, Ti, and Zn particles as well as glass particles which contain other elements, primarily Ca.
- Al and Ag contamination is largely bonded to the silicon surface, while Ti, and Zn, as well as some Ag has been observed as being free particles adhered to the silicon surface.
- NaOH Leaching is efficient for removing contamination correlated with glass fragments primarily Ca, Mg and partial Mn removal.
- Surface impurities such as Al, Zn, and Ag was observed removed from the surface as the surface morphology changed and the samples were rinsed.
- Aqua regia leaching was largely effective at removing Ni, Ag and some other elements. However, it cannot be considered for further development due to difficulty in handling.
- Physical separation by rinsing and filtration was observed to yield a high removal of P, K, Ca, Cu, Zn and Sn and Pb which was unexpected and should be investigated further.

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